

Cultural Influence of Indian Population on Cardiovascular Health: Population Survey

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ABSTRACT

Background: Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain leading cause of death worldwide. Regional food habits, lifestyle and health beliefs shape how individuals manage heart health. Understanding these influences is essential for developing culturally appropriate prevention strategies. **Objective:** This study focuses on how culture and traditions affect heart health, aiming to identify strategies that promote heart-healthy behaviours while respecting traditional practices. **Significance:** Food habits, daily activities, stress management, and how change can affect heart health when consulted with doctors. This study seeks to bridge the gap between modern medical practices and traditional beliefs, enabling more effective health interventions. **Methods:** A survey among 1,000 people from different parts of India was conducted to understand and determine how different traditions and lifestyle might impact to heart-related problems. The questionnaire included demographic information and 13 questions evaluating knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) related to cultural impact on heart health. Statistical methods included Chi-square tests for categorical variables (e.g., healthcare-seeking behaviour), t-tests and ANOVA for numerical variables (e.g., blood pressure, cholesterol), and correlation and regression analysis for identifying links between cultural practices and cardiovascular risk. **Result:** Findings suggests that cultural practices significantly impact cardiovascular health outcomes and this cultural approach should be included in future cardiovascular health initiatives so that it can lead to heart disease prevention in India's diverse population. **Conclusion:** Incorporating culturally sensitive approaches into public health initiatives can enhance awareness and prevention across diverse populations.

Keywords: Cardiovascular diseases, Cultural practices, KAP study, Demographic information

1. Introduction

Heart disease remains one of the leading causes of death worldwide, with its risk factors extending beyond medical conditions to cultural influences and daily habits.^{1,2} Diet, physical activity, stress management, and healthcare-seeking behaviours vary across cultures, shaping cardiovascular health.^{3,4} While some traditions encourage heart-friendly practices, others unknowingly contribute to increased risks through high-sodium diets, sedentary lifestyles, or reliance on alternative medicine.⁵

This study follows the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) model to assess cultural influences on cardiovascular diseases among the Indian population. A survey was conducted across various locations, including colleges and communities, gathering responses from 1,000 participants.⁶ The findings provide valuable insights into how cultural beliefs impact heart health and highlight the need for culturally tailored interventions that promote cardiovascular well-being without disregarding traditional values.⁷⁻⁹

Research shows that culture plays a major role in shaping heart health. Dietary habits influenced by tradition can either protect or increase the risk of cardiovascular diseases. For example, Mediterranean diets rich in fruits, vegetables, and healthy fats are linked to better heart health, whereas diets high in processed foods and saturated fats contribute to heart disease.^{10,11} Lifestyle choices also differ across cultures some communities encourage physical activity as part of daily life, while others have increasingly sedentary routines due to modernization.^{12,13}

Traditional medicine and beliefs also influence how people seek treatment. Some rely on herbal remedies and alternative therapies, often delaying medical care.^{7,14} Cultural attitudes toward stress management further impact heart health, as high-pressure environments and lack of coping mechanisms can lead to increased cardiovascular risk.^{15,16} These factors highlight the need for culturally tailored health interventions that respect traditions while promoting heart-friendly habits.^{9,17}

Our objective is to investigate how cultural beliefs, traditions, and behaviours influence the prevalence, prevention, and management of cardiovascular diseases across different populations, to analyse the impact of cultural dietary habits on heart health, to assess how cultural attitudes shape exercise and physical activity levels, to explore traditional beliefs and their effect on healthcare-seeking behaviour in cardiovascular disease management, to examine cultural perspectives on stress and their influence on cardiovascular risk factors and to propose culturally appropriate strategies to promote heart health while respecting traditional values.^{11,18}

Cardiovascular diseases are often approached with a one-size-fits-all mindset, but people's behaviours and health choices are deeply rooted in culture. Many individuals grow up with traditional foods and ways of living that shape their long-term health.¹⁹ A well-intended public health campaign promoting low-sodium diets or increased exercise may not resonate with certain communities unless it aligns with their cultural norms and values.¹⁴

By understanding these cultural influences, healthcare professionals and policy makers can create more effective, inclusive interventions that do not just instruct but also inspire change.¹³ It is not about asking people to abandon their traditions but finding ways to adapt them for better heart health. This survey aims to bridge the gap between cultural heritage and modern cardiovascular disease prevention, making heart health more accessible and relatable for diverse populations.²⁰

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1. Design of survey

This study employed a quantitative survey design to assess the Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) of participants regarding cultural influences on cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) across five regions of India. The questionnaire consisted of Multiple-Choice Questions. Only individuals who voluntarily agreed to participate were included in this study. The overall goal of this survey was to understand how cultural factors across different regions of India are associated with people's knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to cardiovascular health.

2.2. Validation of Questionnaire

Two experts from the field of clinical research were consulted to assess both content and face validity where experts focused on areas such as relevance and completeness of the questions in addressing the research objectives, Clarity of the language used, ensuring that questions were easily understandable by the target population, Logical flow and structure of the questionnaire, Cultural sensitivity, ensuring that the questions were appropriate for the cultural context of the respondents. Based on their feedback, minor revisions were made to improve question wording, ensure clarity, and enhance the cultural appropriateness of the items. This validation process helped ensure that the final questionnaire was well-suited to capture meaningful and accurate data on the cultural factors influencing cardiovascular health in India.

2.3. Sample Selection

A multi-stage sampling technique was used in this study to collect data from a representative sample of the Indian population in each of the country's five main geographical regions: Northern, Southern, Eastern, Western, and North-Eastern. The objective was to document any possible differences in Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) concerning the impact of culture on cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). A comprehensive study of regional cultural determinants and their relationship to CVD-related KAP is made possible by the selection of participants, which ensured a wide representation of demographic features within each region. A geographically balanced sample that reflected India's cultural diversity was the ultimate goal, while specific sampling techniques within each region may have differed to best fit the local context and accessibility.

2.4. Study Area & Period

Study Area: The study area for the cultural influences on CVDs survey conducted in India, primarily focused on Northern, Southern, Western, Eastern & North-Eastern Regions. **Study Period:** From 21st February 2025 to 4th April 2025.

2.5. Sampling Design & Sample Size

Sampling Design: As part of an observational research data analysis, students from the Gahlot Institute of Pharmacy distributed a structured questionnaire to the general public of different regions in India. **Sample Size:** The survey was conducted among a diverse sample of 1,000 participants across various locations, including colleges and communities, from various regions of India to assess cultural influences on cardiovascular health.

2.6. Data Collection Methods:

There were two sections to the questionnaire.

Section 1: It includes demographic data like name, age, sex, profession, annual family income, current residential state & native state. Section 2: It covers questions related to knowledge, attitude and practice of ‘Cultural Influences on Cardiovascular Diseases’. 13 questions were circulated to people.

2.7. Data Analysis Techniques:

To ensure that the survey findings provide meaningful insights, statistical analysis will be used to determine the significance of cultural influences on cardiovascular health. **Survey Design & Data Collection:** The survey will include structured questionnaires covering dietary habits, exercise routines, stress management, and healthcare-seeking behaviours. Data will be collected from diverse cultural groups to ensure comprehensive representation. **Hypothesis Testing:** The study will test the null hypothesis (H₀: Cultural factors have no significant impact on cardiovascular health) against the alternative hypothesis (H₁: Cultural factors significantly influence cardiovascular health). **Statistical Tests:** **Chi-square tests** will be used to examine categorical variables such as healthcare-seeking behaviours across different cultures. **T-tests and ANOVA** will analyse numerical data such as differences in cholesterol levels and blood pressure among various cultural dietary patterns. **Correlation and Regression Analysis** will help determine relationships between cultural practices and heart disease risk factors. **P-value Interpretation:** A p-value ≤ 0.05 will indicate that the results are statistically significant, suggesting that cultural factors have a real influence on cardiovascular disease prevalence and management. **Data Visualization:** Graphs, charts, and tables will be used to present findings in a clear and accessible manner.

By applying statistical analysis, this study aims to provide evidence-based conclusions that can help develop culturally sensitive healthcare interventions for preventing and managing cardiovascular diseases.

3. RESULTS

3.1 DEMOGRAPHICS

The study sample (N=1002) was predominantly young and female. As shown in **Table 1** and **Table 2**, a significant majority (72.05%) were between the ages of 18 and 25, and 58.48% identified as female. Male participants accounted for 40.51%, and only 0.99% preferred not to disclose their sex. These findings are visually represented in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2**, indicating a sample skewed towards younger females, which may influence the generalizability of the results depending on the context of the study.

Table 1: Age-wise Distribution of Participants

Age	No. of Participants	Percentage
18 - 25	722	72.05
25 - 35	90	8.98
35 - 45	84	8.38
45 - 55	72	7.18
55 and above	34	3.39
Total	1002	100

Figure 1: Age-wise Percentage

Table 2: Sex-wise Distribution of Participants

Sex	No. of Participants	Percentage
Male	406	40.51
Female	586	58.48
Prefer not to say	10	0.99
Total	1002	100

Figure 2: Sex-wise Percentage

The survey was diverse in terms of family income and regional origin. As shown in **Table 3** and **Table 4**, most participants (33.63%) came from families earning between ₹50,000 and ₹2 Lakhs, while 23.65% earned below ₹50,000, and 7.88% had an income above ₹12 Lakhs. Geographically, the majority were from the Western states (80.33%), with smaller representations from the Northern (7.08%), Southern (6.68%), Eastern (4.39%), and North-Eastern (1.49%) states. These patterns are depicted in **Figure 3** and **Figure 4**.

Table 3 : Family Income-wise Distribution of Participants

Family Income	No. of Participants	Percentage
Below 50,000 Rs.	237	23.65
50,000 - 2 Lakhs	337	33.63
2.1 Lakhs - 4 Lakhs	165	16.46
4.1 Lakhs - 8 Lakhs	129	12.87
8.1 Lakhs - 12 Lakhs	55	5.48
Above 12 Lakhs	79	7.88
Total	1002	100

Figure 3: Family Income Distribution Percentage

Table 4: Native State-wise Distribution of Participants

Native State	No. of Participants	Percentage
Northern States	71	7.08
Southern States	67	6.68
Western States	805	80.33
Eastern States	44	4.39
North-Eastern States	15	1.49
Total	1002	100

Figure 4: Native State-wise Distribution Percentage

3.2 CARDIOVASCULAR HEALTH SURVEY DATA INTERPRETATION

3.2.1 NORTHERN REGION

3.2.1.1 Region Vs what type of diet is most common in your culture:

The question aimed to identify the most common type of diet followed in northern regions and its cultural significance. Participants were asked to select the most typical diet in their region, with options like balanced diet, high-carb diet, high-fat diet, and vegetarian/vegan diet. The data in table 5 shows that in the Northern region, a

balanced diet is the most common type, followed by high-carb diets. Fewer people said high-fat or vegetarian/vegan diets are most common. Overall, most people follow balanced eating habits in their culture.

Table 5: Common Diet Types in Region

		What type of diet is most common in your culture?				Total
		Balanced Diet (Fruits, Vegetables, Proteins, etc)	High-Carb Diet (Rice, Bread, etc)	High-Fat Diet (Fried Food, Processed Food, etc)	Vegetarian or Vegan Diet	
Region	North	31	16	13	11	71

Figure 5: Distribution of Common Diet Types

3.2.1.2 Region Vs How often do you consume cultural foods:

The question aimed to understand how often participants consume cultural foods. The data of table 6 shows that people from the Northern region mostly consume cultural foods weekly or occasionally. A smaller number eat them on daily basis, and very few rarely do. This suggests cultural foods are still a regular part of life for many in the region, though not always consumed daily.

Table 6: Frequency of Consumption of Cultural Foods

		How often do you consume cultural foods?				Total
		Daily	Occasionally	Rarely	Weekly	
Region	North	15	20	5	31	71

Figure 6: Frequency Distribution of Cultural Food Consumption in the Northern Region

3.2.1.3 Region vs How does intergenerational influence within your family shape your cardiovascular health habits:

This question aimed to explore how intergenerational influence within families affects participants' cardiovascular health habits. The data in table 7 shows that in the Northern region; most people feel their family's influence moderately shapes their cardiovascular health habits. Some feel strongly influenced, while few of them believe it rarely or doesn't influence them at all. Overall, family plays a noticeable role in shaping heart-health habits for most people in this region.

Table 7: Intergenerational Family Influence on Cardiovascular Health

		How does intergenerational influence within your family shape your cardiovascular health habits?				Total
		Does not Influence at all	Moderately Influences	Rarely Influences	Strongly Influences	
Region	North	6	39	14	12	71
Total		6	39	14	12	71

Figure 7: Intergenerational Family Influence on Cardiovascular Health

3.2.1.4 Region vs Are traditional healers or alternative medicine practitioners trusted more than doctors for cardiovascular health in your culture:

This question examined whether traditional healers or alternative medicine practitioners are trusted more than doctors for cardiovascular health within participants’ cultures. The data in table 8 shows that in the North region; most people trust traditional healers equally to doctors for cardiovascular health. A smaller number trust them more or less than doctors, and very few do not trust them at all. This suggests that traditional or alternative medicine still holds an equal position alongside modern healthcare in the region.

Table 8: Trust in Traditional Healers vs. Doctors

		Are traditional healers or alternative medicine practitioners trusted more than doctors for cardiovascular health in your culture?				Total
		Not Trusted for Cardiovascular Health	Strongly Trusted Over Doctors	Trusted Equally as Doctors	Trusted Less than Doctors	
Region	North	5	16	34	16	71
Total		5	16	34	16	71

Figure 8: Perceived Trust in Traditional Healers Compared to Doctor

3.2.2 SOUTHERN REGION:

3.2.2.1 Region Vs How often do you consume cultural foods:

This question explored how often participants from different regions consume cultural foods, such as Puli hora, Bisi Bele Bath, Mysore Pak, Appam, Idli, Dosa & Sambar, Biryani, Mirchi ka Salan, etc. in southern region. The data from table 9 showed that all 67 participants consume cultural food either weekly or daily. Very few eat them occasionally (14) or rarely (1). This shows that cultural foods are a regular part of life for most people in the South.

Table 9: Frequency of Cultural Food Consumption in the Southern Region

		How often do you consume cultural foods?				Total
		Daily	Occasionally	Rarely	Weekly	
Region	South	19	14	1	33	67
Total		19	14	1	33	67

Figure 9: Consumption Patterns of Cultural Foods

3.2.2.2 Do you have a family history of heart diseases vs What type of diet is most common your culture:

The question examines the relationship between family history of heart disease (such as heart attack or stroke) and the type of diet most common in the participant’s culture. Data in table 10 showed people without a family history of heart disease mostly follow high-carb or balanced diets, while those with a family history often follow high-carb or high-fat diets. Vegetarian and high-protein diets are rare in both groups. The chi-square test ($p = 0.007$) shows a clear link between family history and diet type, meaning people’s diets are related to their family health background.

Table 10: Association Between Family History of Heart Disease and Common Diet

		What type of diet is most common in your culture?					Total
		Balanced Diet (Fruits, Vegetables, Proteins, etc)	High protein	High-Carb Diet (Rice, Bread, etc)	High-Fat Diet (Fried Food, Processed Food, etc)	Vegetarian or Vegan Diet	
Do you have a family history of heart disease (heart attack, stroke, etc.)?	No	12	1	16	1	1	31
	Yes	11	0	11	14	0	36
Total		23	1	27	15	1	67

Figure 10: Comparison of Dietary Patterns Based on Family History of Heart

Table 11 Data analysis

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.941 ^a	4	0.007
Likelihood Ratio	16.820	4	0.002
No. of Valid Cases	67	NA	NA

3.2.2.3 Region vs How does intergenerational influence within your family shape your cardiovascular health habits:

The question explored how intergenerational influence within families affects participants’ cardiovascular health habits in south region. From the data of table 12 Most participants reported that their family moderately influences their heart-health habits. Additionally, 16 participants felt strongly influenced, while 11 reported rare influence, and only 5 felt their family does not influence their cardiovascular behaviour at all.

This indicates that for most individuals in Southern India, family plays a key role in shaping cardiovascular health habits, either through moderate or strong guidance across generations.

Table 12: Intergenerational Family Influence on Cardiovascular Health in the Southern Region

		How does intergenerational influence within your family shape your cardiovascular health habits?				Total
		Does not Influence at all	Moderately Influences	Rarely Influences	Strongly Influences	
Region	South	5	35	11	16	67
Total		5	35	11	16	67

Figure 11: Distribution of Family Influence on Heart-Health Habits

3.2.3 WESTERN REGION

3.2.3.1 Age Vs Do you believe cultural practices influence your dietary habits:

The question assessed whether participants across different age groups believe that cultural practices influence their dietary habits. The data in table 13 shows that most people, especially young adults, believe culture strongly influences their eating habits. The Chi-Square test ($p = 0.045$) shows a clear link between age and this belief. The 18–25 age group shows the strongest belief. So, age seems to affect how people see the role of culture in their diet.

Table 13: Influence of Cultural Practices on Dietary Habits by Age Group

		Do you believe cultural practices influence your dietary habits?			Total
		No	Not Sure	Yes	
Age:	18 - 25	52	72	492	616
	25 - 35	10	9	43	62
	35 - 45	11	9	43	63
	45 - 55	1	6	36	43
	55 and above	3	0	18	21
Total		77	96	632	805

Figure 12: Age-wise Distribution of Beliefs About Cultural Influence on Diet

Table 14: Data analysis

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.820 ^a	8	0.045
Likelihood Ratio	18.050	8	0.021
No. of Valid Cases	805	NA	NA

3.2.3.2 Do you have a family history of heart disease (heart attack, stroke, etc.)? vs What type of diet is most common in your culture:

The question aimed to explore whether having a family history of heart disease (e.g., heart attack or stroke) is associated with the type of diet most common in a person’s culture. According to table 15, People with a family history of heart disease are more likely to follow high-fat or high-carb diets, while those without it tend to eat more balanced diets. The Chi-Square test ($p < .001$) shows a strong link between diet type and family history of heart disease. This means diet habits clearly differ between the two groups.

Table 15: Relationship Between Family History of Heart Disease and Common Diets

		What type of diet is most common in your culture?						Total
		Balanced Diet (Fruits, Vegetables, Proteins, etc)	High protein	High-Carb Diet (Rice, Bread, etc)	High-fat diet, vegetarian with fruits and vegetables	High-Fat Diet (Fried Food, Processed Food, etc)	Vegetarian or Vegan Diet	
Do you have a family history of heart disease (heart attack, stroke, etc.)?	No	249	1	152	1	87	67	557
	Yes	80	0	85	0	65	18	248
Total		329	1	237	1	152	85	805

Figure 13: Distribution of Common Diet Types by Family History of Heart Disease

Table 16: Data Analysis

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.129 ^a	5	<0.001
Likelihood Ratio	24.628	5	<0.001
No. of Valid Cases	805	NA	NA

3.2.3.3 Family Income (Rs. per Annum) vs Are preventive health measures like regular check-ups encouraged in your culture:

The question assessed how family income levels (in ₹ per annum) relate to whether preventive health measures, such as regular medical check-ups, are encouraged in participants' cultures. According to the data in table 17, people with higher incomes are more likely to value and follow preventive health habits. Lower-income groups show less consistent encouragement, possibly due to financial or cultural barriers. The results ($p = .011$ and $.010$) show a clear link between income and attitudes toward preventive health.

Table 17: Cultural Encouragement of Preventive Health Measures by Family Income

		Are preventive health measures like regular check-ups encouraged in your culture?				Total
		Not Encouraged	Not Sure	Occasionally Encouraged	Strongly Encouraged	
Family Income (Rs. per Annum)	2.1 Lakhs - 4 Lakhs	17	8	62	29	116
	4.1 Lakhs - 8 Lakhs	16	6	48	28	98
	50,000 - 2 Lakhs	33	18	135	96	282
	8.1 Lakhs - 12 Lakhs	9	6	26	6	47
	Above 12 Lakhs	7	5	18	23	53
	Below 50,000	31	31	86	61	209
Total		113	74	375	243	805

Figure 14: Preventive Health Attitudes Across Income

Table 18: Data analysis

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30.136 ^a	15	0.011
Likelihood Ratio	30.478	15	0.010
No. of Valid Cases	805	NA	NA

3.2.4 EASTERN REGION:

3.2.4.1 Region Vs What type of diet is most common in your culture

The question explored the type of diet most common in the culture of respondents from the Eastern region of India. According to the data in table 19, the most common diets are high-carb (19 people) and balanced diets (12 people). Fewer people follow high-fat (8) or vegetarian/vegan (4) diets, and 1 person reported no specific diet. This shows that carb-rich and balanced diets are the most common in the East.

Table 19: Common Cultural Diet Types in the Eastern Region

		What type of diet is most common in your culture?					Total
		Balanced Diet (Fruits, Vegetables, Proteins, etc)	High-Carb Diet (Rice, Bread, etc)	High-Fat Diet (Fried Food, Processed Food, etc)	nothing	Vegetarian or Vegan Diet	
Region	East	12	19	8	1	4	44
Total		12	19	8	1	4	44

Figure 15: Distribution of Cultural Diet Preferences

3.2.4.2 Region vs How often do you consume cultural foods

The question investigated how often people from the Eastern region of India consume traditional or cultural foods, with examples provided (e.g., Litti Chokha, Sattu, Momo, Rasgulla, etc.). According to the data in table 20, most consume cultural foods occasionally (17) or daily (12). Fewer eat them weekly (10) or rarely (5). This shows that cultural foods are a regular part of life for most people in the East.

Table 20: Frequency of Cultural Food Consumption

		How often do you consume cultural foods?				Total
		Daily	Occasionally	Rarely	Weekly	
Region	East	12	17	5	10	44
Total		12	17	5	10	44

Figure 16: Cultural Food Consumption Patterns

3.2.5 NORTH-EASTERN REGION:

3.2.5.1 Family Income (Rs. per Annum) vs Are preventive health measures like regular check-ups encouraged in your culture:

The question explored how family income influences the encouragement of preventive health measures, such as regular check-ups, within participants' cultures. The data in table 21 shows that cultural support for preventive health habits like check-ups tends to rise with income. Higher-income families are more likely to strongly encourage these practices, while lower-income groups show less consistent support. This may be due to money, access, or cultural factors. Overall, there is a clear link between income and how much preventive health is encouraged.

Table 21: Family Income and Cultural Encouragement of Preventive Health Measures

		Are preventive health measures like regular check-ups encouraged in your culture?			Total
		Not Encouraged	Occasionally Encouraged	Strongly Encouraged	
Family Income (Rs. per Annum)	2.1 Lakhs - 4 Lakhs	0	4	1	5
	50,000 - 2 Lakhs	1	4	0	5
	Above 12 Lakhs	0	0	3	3
	Below 50,000	1	1	0	2
Total		2	9	4	15

Figure 17: Encouragement of Preventive Health by Family Income

Table 22: Data analysis

Chi-Square Tests				
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.750 ^a	6	0.033	0.027
Likelihood Ratio	15.048	6	0.020	0.023
No. of Valid Cases	15	NA	NA	NA

4. Discussion

Culture strongly influences diet and heart health awareness, especially among younger individuals and those in the West. People with a family history of heart disease often follow riskier diets, highlighting the need for better nutrition education. Traditional food habits remain strong, so health advice should align with cultural practices. Preventive care is more common among higher-income groups, particularly in the West. Trust in traditional healers remains high, suggesting they can be valuable partners in promoting heart health. Spiritual beliefs also shape health views, notably in the North-East and West.

5. Conclusion

The findings of this survey highlight the significant role of cultural influences on heart health behaviors across India. Key factors such as dietary habits, stress management, and healthcare-seeking behavior are strongly shaped by traditional practices and beliefs. Despite the advancement of modern healthcare, many people continue to hold on to cultural traditions, including reliance on traditional healers and practices.

These results suggest that future health programs aimed at improving cardiovascular health should not only consider modern medical advice but also respect cultural values and incorporate community practices. Engaging with traditional healers and understanding cultural norms will be essential to making heart health messages more effective and ensuring their acceptance in diverse communities.

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Table No.	TABLE NAME (CAPTION)
1	Age-wise Distribution of Participants
2	Sex-wise Distribution of Participants
3	Family Income-wise Distribution of Participants
4	Native State-wise Distribution of Participants
5	Common Diet Types in Region
6	Frequency of Consumption of Cultural Foods
7	Intergenerational Family Influence on Cardiovascular Health
8	Trust in Traditional Healers vs. Doctors
9	Frequency of Cultural Food Consumption in the Southern Region
10	Association Between Family History of Heart Disease and Common Diet
11	Data analysis
12	Intergenerational Family Influence on Cardiovascular Health in the Southern Region
13	Influence of Cultural Practices on Dietary Habits by Age Group
14	Data analysis
15	Relationship Between Family History of Heart Disease and Common Diets
16	Data analysis
17	Cultural Encouragement of Preventive Health Measures by Family Income
18	Data analysis
19	Common Cultural Diet Types in the Eastern Region
20	Frequency of Cultural Food Consumption
21	Family Income and Cultural Encouragement of Preventive Health Measures
22	Data analysis

Figure No.	FIGURE NAME (CAPTION)
1	Age-wise Percentage
2	Sex-wise Percentage
3	Family Income Distribution Percentage
4	Native State-wise Distribution Percentage
5	Distribution of Common Diet Types
6	Frequency Distribution of Cultural Food Consumption in the Northern Region
7	Intergenerational Family Influence on Cardiovascular Health
8	Perceived Trust in Traditional Healers Compared to Doctor
9	Consumption Patterns of Cultural Foods
10	Comparison of Dietary Patterns Based on Family History of Heart
11	Distribution of Family Influence on Heart-Health Habits
12	Age-wise Distribution of Beliefs About Cultural Influence on Diet
13	Distribution of Common Diet Types by Family History of Heart Disease
14	Preventive Health Attitudes Across Income
15	Distribution of Cultural Diet Preferences
16	Cultural Food Consumption Patterns
17	Encouragement of Preventive Health by Family Income